

A Comparative Study of Functional and Radiological Outcome of Hoffa Fracture Treated with Cannulated Cancellous Screw (CCS) and Buttressing Plate versus Cannulated Cancellous Screw Alone

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Abstract:

Purpose and objective: Hoffa fracture is a femoral condyle fracture in the coronal plane. The lateral condyle is more commonly involved. This study aimed to compare the functional and radiological results of surgical treatment for Hoffa fractures with CCS and buttressing plate versus CCS alone.

Methodology: This was a prospective study conducted from March 2023 to March 2024 in orthopaedic department of Gauhati Medical College and Hospital, Assam. This study includes 20 patients with Hoffa fracture out of which 10 treated with CCS and buttressing plate and other 10 treated with CCS alone. Radiological and functional outcome, Range of motion (ROM) and knee society score (KSS) of patients were evaluated at the 4- and 12-month follow-up examination.

Results: 4 months after the surgery, markedly improved outcomes were observed in the CCS and buttressing plate group vs CCS group regarding ROM (122 +/-5 vs 110+/-8) AND KSS (85 +/-5 vs 78 +/-4). In the 12 months follow-up after surgery, significantly improved outcomes were sustained in the CCS with buttressing plate vs CCS group regarding ROM (128+/-5 vs 122+/-5) and KSS (89+/-5 vs 83+/-4). By the final follow-up, all patients had achieved normal healing with no instances of malunion, non-union or reduction loss.

Conclusion: Fixation of Hoffa fracture with CCS and buttressing plate is more effective and reliable as compared to CCS alone.

Keywords: Hoffa fracture, Cannulated Cancellous Screw, Buttressing plate.

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Introduction

A Hoffa fracture is a form of a coronal plane fracture affecting the posterior part of the femoral condyle and is often accompanied by a femoral shaft fracture. [1] Hoffa fracture accounts for about 8.7% to 13% of most distal femur fractures. The Orthopaedic Trauma Association has identified Hoffa fractures as Type 33-B3 fractures.

These fractures usually originate from motor vehicle accidents or falls from heights, albeit the exact mechanism causing them is yet unknown. The lateral condyle of the distal femur is usually more affected than the medial condyle mainly due to the physiological genu valgum of the knee. Patients commonly present in the hospital with sudden onset of pain, crepitus and progressive

swelling around knee joint with decreased knee joint mobility, and floating patella test is found to be positive. Hoffa fractures are uncommon and challenging to diagnose; while oblique, lateral, and anteroposterior view radiographs may be useful, a computed tomography (CT) scan is advised if the diagnosis is unclear.

Complications with conservative therapy of this fracture include non-union, malunion, and stiffness in the knee. Because of the strain of the muscles and the instability of the bone, this fracture is naturally unstable. Anatomical reduction and firm internal fixation are advised for the management of this fracture because conservative treatment produces poor results. [2] The goal of this present

study was to compare the clinical outcomes of surgical treatment with cannulated compression screws and buttress plate (CCS plus BP) versus cannulated compression screws only (CCS) in a consecutive series of patients with Hoffa fracture.

Study population

This is a prospective study which was carried out in the Orthopaedic Department of Gauhati Medical College and Hospital in Assam between March 2023 and March 2024. It involved 20 patients with Hoffa fractures who were treated with open reduction and internal fixation (ORIF) using cannulated compression screws fixation with buttress plating (CCS plus BP) against cannulated compression screws fixation alone (CCS) at the Department of Orthopaedics, Gauhati Medical College and Hospital. [3]

Inclusion criteria: (1) Patients who are over 18 years old or who have reached skeletal maturity at the time of surgical; (2) Hoffa fracture diagnosis at the time of presentation; (3) Any form of surgical treatment received within three weeks of injury; and (4) Patients must consent to follow-up for a minimum of 12 months Exclusion criteria for the study were as follows: (1) Patients who are under 18 years old; (2) Open fractures; (3) Pathological fractures; (4) fail to follow-up; (5) insufficient

clinical data; and (6) conservative treatment (non-surgical).

All of the patients who were chosen for the study had to have surgery unless, in extremely rare circumstances, they had open fractures, were too sick to undergo surgery, had pathological fractures, had previously had knee joint surgery, had any type of neurovascular injury to a lower limb, or had knee pathology that affected their functional status. All cases were initially managed with above knee slab and painkillers, and then all routine investigations for surgery were carried out. [4] The hospital ethics committee has approved the trial, and all subjects provided written informed consent.

Preoperative planning

Pre-anaesthesia examinations were carried out on each case to determine whether the patient was generally fit for operation. Along with Digital X-ray (Fig 2) and CT with 3-dimensional reconstructed images (Fig 1) of the affected knee joint, data about patient demographics, the mechanism of injury, and clinical results (bone union [revealed by radiography], range of movement [ROM], and Knee Society Scores [KSS]) were collected for the purpose of surgical planning. [5]

Figure 1: Preoperative computed tomography images of the knee showing lateral condyle Hoffa fracture

Figure 2: Preoperative radiographs of the knee (Anteroposterior and Lateral view), showing lateral condyle Hoffa fracture

Surgical technique

All the surgical procedures were carried out in the Department of Orthopaedics, Gauhati Medical College and Hospital, under general or spinal anaesthesia according to patient's general conditions.

Based on the position of the Hoffa fracture (medial or lateral), a posteromedial or posterolateral approach was made accordingly (Fig 3). Following parapatellar release, the patella was either medially or laterally dislocated to fully exposed the fractured

condyle of the femur.[6] By flexing the knee at 30 degree, the Hoffa fracture fragment was initially reduced and was secured preliminarily using two Kirschner wires (Fig 4). Based on the fracture line and fragments, two cannulated compression screws (CCS) were placed in either anteroposterior or posteroanterior direction.[7] If the Hoffa fracture remained unstable following CCS fixation, a locking buttress plate (Fig 5) was placed on the posterior side of the fractured condyle to provide angular stability.(8)(Fig 6)

Figure 3: Intraoperative image showing incision site

Figure 4: Radiograph showing Hoffa fracture being fixed using two Kirschner wires

Figure 5: Radiographs showing placing of buttress plate

Figure 6: Radiographs showing a buttress plate with CCS

Follow-up, evaluation and rehabilitation

Postoperative X-rays were taken on the first postoperative day (Fig 7 and Fig 8). All patients were followed up at 4 and 12 months after surgery for physical examination and X-ray were conducted.

[13] All patients were assessed radiologically, clinically as well as functionally using Knee Society Score (KSS). Range of movement (ROM) of the knee joint and bone union. [9] Under the guidance of a physiotherapist, every patient adhered to a methodical rehabilitation regimen to restore optimal function to their knee joint. In summary, all patients began knee joint workouts three days after

surgery using a constantly passive motion device. Two weeks post-surgery, continuous passive movement of the knee was gradually increased from 20–40 degrees to 50–100 degree depending on the patient's varying degree of knee pain. In the 2–6 weeks postoperative period, patients started performing exercises on beds without bearing weight. Patients were not allowed to weight-bear of the operated limb for the initial 6 weeks after surgery. [10] Eight to twelve weeks later, patients were permitted to advance to partial weight-bearing walking exercises. From 4 postoperative months after surgery, complete weight bearing was permitted, provided that X-ray showed bone union.

Figure 7: Post OP radiographs showing buttress plate with CCS

Figure 8: Post OP radiograph showing CCS fixation

Results

A total of 20 consecutive patients with Hoffa fractures underwent open reduction and internal fixation. The cohort included 13 males and 7 females, aged between 19 and 57 years (see Table 1). Of these patients, 15 sustained their injuries from motor vehicle accidents, while 5 had history of self falls. The patients were divided into two groups: 10 received treatment with CSS plus BP (7 males and 3 females, aged 21–57 years) and rest 10 received CSS fixation alone (6 males and 4 females, aged 19–48 years). The two groups did not differ statistically significantly in terms of age, sex, fracture side, or injury mechanism (Table 1). The mean duration of surgery and blood loss were much greater in the CSS plus BP group compared to the CSS-only group, with surgery lasting a mean of 93 minutes (range 80–110) versus 67 minutes (range 60–82), and mean blood loss of 82 ml (range 75–98) versus 71 ml (range 65–81) respectively. [11] The direction of the screw fixation (anterior to

posterior) did not show a significant difference between the groups. At 4 months post-surgery follow up evaluation, the mean ROM of knee was 122 ± 5 degrees in the CSS plus BP group (Fig 11) and 110 ± 8 degrees in the CSS-only group (Fig 10), while the mean KSS was found to be 85 ± 5 in the CSS plus BP group and 78 ± 4 in the CSS-only group, indicating superior ROM and KSS values for the CSS plus BP group (Table 2). [12]

At the 12-month follow-up evaluation, significant differences in terms of ROM (128 ± 5 versus 122 ± 5) and KSS (89 ± 5 versus 83 ± 4) persisted between the two groups (Table 2). Postoperative radiographs confirmed that all patients had achieved proper anatomical reduction with stable fixation (Fig 9). By the final follow-up, all patients exhibited normal fracture healing without any sign of non-union, malunion, delayed union or reduction loss. There was no statistically significant difference in the time required for bone union between the two treatment groups.[13]

Figure 9: Post OP radiograph at 4 months

Table 1: Demographic and clinical data at presentation of patients

Characteristic	Treatment group	
	CCS plus BP	CCS only
	N=10	N=10
Age, years	21- 57	19-48
Sex		
Male	7	6
Female	3	4
Anatomical side		
Left	4	7
Right	6	3
Mechanism of injury		
Vehicle	7	8
Falling	3	2

Graph 1: Demographic and clinical data at presentation of patients

Table 2: Clinical outcomes of patients treated for Hoffa fracture

Characteristic	Treatment group		
	CCS +BP	CCS only	Statistical significance
	N=10	N=10	
Duration of surgery, min	93 (range 80–110)	67 (range 60–82)	p<0.003
Blood loss, ml	82 ml (range 75–98)	71 (range 65–81)	p<0.002
Screw direction			
AP	9	8	NS
PA	1	2	NS
Knee ROM (degree)			
4 months	122 +/- 5	110 +/- 8	p<0.001
12 months	128 +/- 5	122 +/- 5	p<0.005
KSS points			
4 months	85 +/- 5	78 +/- 4	p<0.001
12 months	89 +/-5	83 +/-4	p<0.001
Stability			
Yes	10	10	NS
No	0	0	NS
Time to bone union, months	3.5 +/- 1.1	4 +/- 1.3	NS

Data are present as n (%) or mean ± SD, AP: antero-posterior; PA: postero-anterior; ROM: range of motion; KSS: knee society score. NS, no statistically significant between-group difference (P>0.05)

Fig 10: Images of postoperative 4 months (fixed with CCS only)

Fig 11: Images of postoperative 4 months (fixed with CSS plus BP)

Discussion

The Hoffa fracture, recognized as an intraarticular coronal fracture of the distal femur, continues to be one of the most challenging fractures to manage. Because of the unsatisfactory results and non-union that conservative management has demonstrated, open reduction with internal fixation (ORIF) is necessary for achieving successful clinical results. [14] The standard method of treated Hoffa fracture is internal reduction with screw fixation which is undergoing continual improvement. In order to achieve compression between the fragments, at least two screws that vertically crosses the fracture line should be used to give biomechanical support. One crucial element in healing of fractures is fixation stability.

Positive biomechanical and clinical investigations have showed that a buttress plate might give the Hoffa fracture greater stability and was linked to positive clinical outcomes in order to increase the purchase for fixing. The current study involved 20 individuals in total, and their baseline demographic and clinical parameters did not show any statistically significant difference between the two patient groups. Compared to the CSS group, the duration of surgery and blood loss were notably greater in the CSS plus BP group. [15] This was due to the additional time and larger incision required to position the plate, leading to extended operating time and increased blood loss. At the four- and twelve-month follow-ups, patients in the CSS plus BP group showed better range of movement (ROM) and knee society score (KSS) values compared to the CSS group; however, the gap between the two groups diminished over time. Because the plate offers more support and may keep the fragment from migrating upward, preserving postoperative stability, the patients may have had better results. At the final follow-up, all patients in the current study exhibited normal fracture healing; however, those in the CSS plus BP group demonstrated better outcomes in terms of range of movement (ROM) and knee society score (KSS) values. These findings imply that using a plate in the treatment of Hoffa fractures may result in better fixation stability and results. [16] There were several factors which limited the result of the study. First, the trial's sample size was relatively small because Hoffa fractures are quite rare. Secondly, because this was a retrospective study, outcomes could have been skewed by selection bias. In conclusion, CSS fixation with buttress plating for Hoffa fractures has been demonstrated to be a more effective treatment method for these patients. It may also offer better stability and results than using CSS screws alone in terms of ROM and KSS.

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